

Laser Photoacoustic Spectroscopy of Azulene[†]

D. KUMAR, R. V. NAUMAN, T. L. MATHERS and S. P. MCGLYNN*

Chemistry Department, The Louisiana State University, Baton Rouge, LA 70803, U.S.A.

and

R. MOHANTY

Physics Department, Southern University, Baton Rouge, LA 70813, U.S.A.

The purpose of this work is to present a simple, inexpensive technique, one based on analog circuitry, which (i) corrects laser induced signals (photogalvanic, photoacoustic, fluorescence or whatever) on a pulse-by-pulse basis for the fluctuations of the individual excitation pulses and (ii) is applicable to both linear and non-linear processes. This technique is demonstrated by photoacoustic spectroscopic (PAS) investigations of azulene, it being thought that the numerous questions besetting the electronic spectroscopy of this molecule might yield to PAS probings. The O₀ bands of the S₁←S₀ and S₂←S₀ transitions are presented at high resolution and the former is shown to contain four difference progressions. Comparison of PAS and absorption spectra (AS) suggests an onset of either photochemistry or luminescence upon excitation of the 1484 cm⁻¹ a₁ fundamental of the S₁ state. A new method for measuring fluorescence quantum yields is presented and discussed.

PHOTOACOUSTIC spectroscopy (PAS) is a sensitive monitor of non-radiative, energy-degradative pathways. Unfortunately, PAS technology has had to await the development of tunable lasers, sensitive microphones and piezoelectric transducers. With their advent, PAS has realised some of its potential, and various ways have been developed¹ for optimising the signals of gaseous, liquid and solid samples, as well as those of optically dense and/or scattering media.

Pulsed lasers, however, are characterised by high peak-powers and low duty-cycles. They also suffer from poor pulse-to-pulse power stability which, along with the low duty-cycle, can pose serious signal extraction problems. One may have to resort to box-car integrators with large effective time-constants and to extremely-slow scan speeds in order to extract the detailed spectroscopic structure. Alternatively, expensive, computer-based, digital data acquisition systems may be used to maximise the system resolution. The technique described here² is different in that it corrects the individual signals for laser power fluctuations, on a pulse-by-pulse basis, and is based on simple analog circuitry. It is a considerable improvement over conventional analog systems because it forces the duty-cycle towards unity. It is also applicable both to linear and non-linear spectroscopic measurements.

Azulene provides a sensitive test of spectrometer capabilities because of the many questions that beset its electronic spectroscopy. For example, azulene fluorescence is anomalous³⁻⁵, being S₂→S₀ rather than S₁→S₀; few, if any, triplet states have been established with any certainty; and, finally, the S₂←S₀ emissive/absorptive events do not exhibit

the Lewschin mirror-image characteristic⁶. Despite extensive study⁷⁻¹², these problems remain largely unsettled.

It seemed that PAS, by virtue of its unique capabilities, could provide answer to some of the above questions. This inference is based on the following statements.

(i) The putative S₁→S₀ non-emissivity requires that, in the absence of any λ-dependent photochemistry, the S₁↔S₀ absorption and PA spectra be identical.

(ii) The complexity of the S₂←S₀ absorption band has been attributed to a vibronic coupling of S₂ and S₄ states mediated by a₁ normal modes. If such be the case, the non-radiative energy transfer that occurs to the adjoining manifold of rovibronic states built on S₀, S₁, or T₁ states of lower or comparable energy from the pure S₂ states might be expected to differ from that arising in vibronically-contaminated S₂ states. That is, if the S₂←S₀ absorption band is as complicated as is supposed, transfer probabilities within it need not be uniform and one should see differences between the PAS and absorption spectra.

(iii) If, in fact, the S₁→S₀ quantum yield is zero, then the S₂→S₀ quantum yield (the value of which, φ_F≅0.03, is both very low and quite uncertain¹³) should be independently determinable from S₂←S₀ and S₁←S₀ PAS data.

(iv) The origin band of the S₁←S₀ transition exhibits considerable hot band activity and it is difficult to analyse. The greater resolution of laser PAS should facilitate such an analysis.

[†] Dedicated to Professor Sadhan Basu on the occasion of his 65th birthday.

Thus, the purpose of this work is to describe a recently-constructed photoacoustic spectrometer and to examine its performance by addressing the electronic spectroscopy of the azulene molecule.

Experimental

The photoacoustic spectrometer^a is shown schematically in Fig. 1. The excitation source is a Chromatix CMX-4 flash-lamp pumped, tunable dye laser of pulse width $\sim 1 \mu\text{s}$, peak power $\sim 6\text{-}8 \text{ kW}$ and band width $\sim 3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (without etalon) or $0.1\text{-}0.2 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (with etalon). The pulse generator produces a sequence of pairs of pulses R (reset) and T (trigger), both $10\text{-}15 \mu\text{s}$ wide, at some predetermined rate (upto 30 pairs/s). The R pulse resets the box-car integrator (PAR model 160, suitably modified by addition of an electronic switch to the integrator board) and the peak detector. The T pulse, positioned on the trailing edge of the R pulse, triggers the laser and the box-car integrator.

Fig. 1. Schematic of PA spectrometer: (G) OMX-4 internal gate signal, (R) reset pulse, (T) trigger pulse, (L) laser beam, (F) filter, (BS) beam-splitter, (M) microphone, (PM) photomultiplier tube, and (DL) hollow cathode discharge lamp. Amplifier 3 is followed by a rectifier and filter to convert AO into unidirectional signals. Amplifier 2 incorporates a simple RC integrator to give total pulse energy for each pulse.

The box-car, operated at very low time-constant, behaves much like a gated detector. The box-car gate is set on the first peak of the damped, acoustic ringing signal generated in the microphone. The peak-detector gets its reference signal from the photomultiplier tube, which is a wideband GaAs photocathode with nearly-flat response. Since the PA signal is proportional to laser pulse energy (*i.e.* not to peak intensity), the amplifier AMP2 contains an RC integrator ($\tau \sim 20 \mu\text{s}$) which generates a pulse, the height of which is proportional to total pulse energy. Hence, for a given laser pulse, the box-car integrator, the peak detector and the analog divider generate signals A, B and A/B, respectively, all of which are held constant over the repetition time interval between the laser pulses (100 ms at 10 pps rate). Immediately prior to T-triggering of the

next laser pulse, the R-pulse resets (*i.e.* 'zeroes') both the peak detector and the box-car so that they are conditioned for that laser pulse. This arrangement produces a sequence of normalised A/B signals at the analog divider output and maintains each of these signals constant over the time interval between pulses. That is, the effective duty cycle approaches unity. The resultant pulse train is averaged by an RC integrator, the smooth signal from which is then fed to one channel of a dual pen X-Y recorder. The second channel of the X-Y recorder displays the wavelength calibration markers that are generated by the photogalvanic effect in a neon hollow cathode discharge lamp. The AUTO-SCAN scans the laser at predetermined scan speeds (cm^{-1}/s) and also, through TTL control, activates the time-base and the pen-down mechanism of the X-Y recorder.

Excessively strong or weak pulses are eliminated from the A/B train by CMOS switches. These switches, activated by voltage comparators, monitor the over-voltage at A, B and A/B and the under-range at B. This procedure ensures that the analog divider operates in a linear range, with the result that smooth A/B output is obtained not only in the presence of large pulse fluctuations but even in the presence of 'misfires'. The voltage comparators also provide a visual indication of level-excess problems by activating a set of LED's. The non-radiative detection sensitivity of the apparatus is obtained from the absorbance data for azulene (assuming negligible $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ emissivity) and is better than $10^{-9} \text{ J per pulse}$.

The advantage of this inexpensive equipment is its ability to normalise the signal, on a pulse-by-pulse basis. In addition, the improvement in duty-cycle and the ability to study non-linear processes (by replacing the analog divider module by an analog multi-function module capable of exponentiating voltages to arbitrary powers) can be matched only by expensive microprocessor-based, data-acquisition systems.

The sample cell, 1 mm thickness, is shown in Fig. 2. It is used at Brewster angles in order to minimise window reflection losses. The all-quartz construction reduces background to insignificant values. The dead space in the connecting tube is minimised in order to increase system sensitivity. Window deposition of condensable vapors is prevented by window temperatures that are slightly greater than that of the cell body. The contact gas, either argon or nitrogen, is held at atmospheric pressure. The cell is thoroughly purged with the contact gas prior to all measurements. The microphone is a Knowles Electronics BT 1759 with built-in pre-amplifier.

Azulene is purified by vacuum sublimation at temperature differentials of $25\text{-}30^\circ$. The process is slow but it produces long, thin, pure, wafer-like azulene crystals.

Fig. 2. Schematic of PA cell. A 2.5 cm diameter, 1 mm thick standard quartz absorption cell was fitted, as shown, with a 5 cm long quartz tube. The end of this tube was tapered to receive the microphone carriage. (M) microphone, (B) teflon block, (S) stainless steel plates, 1/16" thick, (O) O-ring seal for microphone cavity, (T) thin teflon diaphragm supported by O-ring, O', (C) thin channel, 0.2 mm diameter, and (V) vent hole.

Results and Discussion

$S_1 \leftrightarrow S_0$ transition :

Sensitivity of PAS : PA and absorption spectra of the $S_1 \leftrightarrow S_0$ transition of gaseous azulene are shown in Fig. 3. The resolution of this spectrum in a 1 mm path is considerably better than that reported by Hunt and Ross⁷ who used a 4 m absorption path length, higher concentrations of azulene and photographic plates. That is, the sensitivity of the PA spectrometer is some 10^6 times greater than that of the absorption system used by Ross and, additionally, it exhibits improved resolution. Modern spectrophotometers (e.g. Cary 217) cannot remotely approach this sensitivity even at one-tenth the resolution. That is, the PA technique has enormous analytic potential.

The origin band : The temperature dependence of the PA $S_1 \leftrightarrow S_0$ origin is shown in Fig. 4. Two sequence intervals had been reported previously⁶. However, the data of Fig. 4 suggest four such intervals. A good gaussian analysis is obtained by choosing the origin at 14 294.9 cm^{-1} , individual band half-widths of 8 cm^{-1} and four progressions of -7.4 (6 members), -50.1 (4 members), +7.1 (3 members) and +28.2 cm^{-1} (4 members), respectively.

Several attempts^{7,9,11} to assign the normal modes of azulene in S_0 and S_1 states are available. The following considerations, then, are pertinent to the

Fig. 3. (a) Partial gas-phase PA spectrum of azulene $S_1 \leftarrow S_0$; $T=61^\circ$; N_2 'contact' gas; $p=1$ atm. The superposed vertical pips are the neon calibration markers; laser bandwidth=3 cm^{-1} , pulse repetition rate=10 pps, laser scan speed=1 cm^{-1}/s , time-constant for final averaging=1 s. Broken line indicates a gap in the spectrum due to low power of the laser dye in this wavelength region. (b) Partial gas-phase absorption spectrum of the $S_1 \leftarrow S_0$ transition of azulene. The PA spectrum is recorded on a linear scale whereas the absorption spectrum is on a logarithmic scale.

assignment of the sequences observed in the $S_1 \leftarrow S_0$ transitions.

(i) There is temptation to associate the -7.4 cm^{-1} sequence with the ninth a_1 mode (1 396 cm^{-1} in S_0) because of the general activity of this vibration in the $S_1 \leftarrow S_0$ transition. However, the S_0/S_1 decrement⁷ in this mode in the gas phase is only 1 cm^{-1} and, besides, the rather high energy of 1 400 cm^{-1} is inconsistent with the extensive hot band activity of this sequence. The temperature dependency of this sequence suggests a low-energy mode, either one of the a_2 modes (189 and 331 cm^{-1} in S_0 , respectively)⁹ or one of the b_2 modes (240 and 304 cm^{-1} in S_0 , respectively)⁹.

(ii) The -50.1 cm^{-1} sequence could correspond to either the fourth or fifth a_1 normal modes (900 and 971 cm^{-1} in S_0 , respectively) because these exhibit S_0/S_1 decrements of 41 and 59 cm^{-1} , respectively, in the gas phase⁹. However, the temperature dependency of the first sequence member suggests

Fig. 4. Photoacoustic spectra of the $S_1 \leftarrow S_0$ origin band of azulene at 50 and 35°. The computer fit and the various series of vibrational difference bands are also shown. To add $14\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ to each abscissal energy in order to get absolute energies.

a vibrational energy of $400\text{--}500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and eliminates these possibilities. Nor does the first a_1 normal mode (406 cm^{-1} in S_0) suffice because this mode exhibits⁹ an S_0/S_1 decrement of $22\text{--}24\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Consequently, the best assignment for this sequence, given that 10% S_0/S_1 frequency decrements are not uncommon, is either the third a_2 or b_2 normal modes (542 and 562 cm^{-1} in S_0 , respectively)¹⁰.

(iii) The rapid increase with temperature of the $14\,277\text{ cm}^{-1}$ band relative to the $14\,285\text{ cm}^{-1}$ band is undoubtedly attributable to the 406 cm^{-1} (in S_0) vibrational mode discussed immediately above.

(iv) The sequences that lie at higher energy than the O,O band are the ones with the greater physical implications. The $+7.1$ and $+28.2\text{ cm}^{-1}$ sequence energies correspond rather well with the S_0/S_1 increments of 8 and 23 cm^{-1} observed in gas-phase azulene for the two lowest-energy b_1 normal modes^{9,11}. Furthermore, the energies of these normal modes are not inconsistent with observed temperature dependencies.

S_1 emissivity or photochemistry: The PAS and AS are compared in Fig. 3. On the whole, the AS and PAS of the $S_1 \leftarrow S_0$ transition are remarkably similar, a fact that suggests that the S_1 state is either largely non-emissive or emissive only from the O,O origin band.

There is, however, an anomaly at $1\,580\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (i.e. in the 4th band of the $S_1 \leftarrow S_0$ transition). The relative decrease of intensity of this band in PAS suggests that energy absorbed in this band is converted into either luminescence or photochemical reaction. Since an infrared CH vibrational emission of azulene has been reported¹² following $S_1 \leftarrow S_0$ excitation, it is not unreasonable to suggest that the $1\,580\text{ cm}^{-1}$ anomaly, pertaining as it does to a CH-active mode, is corroborative of the infrared emission. Furthermore, it is implied by these PAS data that the quantum yields of this ir CH emission process are non-uniform throughout the $S_1 \leftarrow S_0$ absorption band.

$S_2 \leftrightarrow S_0$ transition:

Vibronic coupling: The $S_2 \leftarrow S_0$ origin band in the PA spectrum is shown in Fig. 5. Unlike $S_1 \leftarrow S_0$, no progressions on the higher frequency side of the assigned O-O band are observed. The lower resolution evident in this spectrum is attributable, in part

Fig. 5. Photoacoustic spectrum of the $S_2 \leftarrow S_0$ origin band of azulene at 50° in the presence of argon at 1 atm pressure

at least, to the frequency doubling required for higher energies. A lack of synchrony between the scan rate of the doubling crystal and that of the laser fundamental caused a loss of power in the 2nd harmonic, with the result that the spectrum had to be 'patched-up' from short, isolated scans. By this means, most of the $S_2 \leftarrow S_0$ region was recorded. No discrepancies that would suggest any variation of quantum yield throughout this excitation region were found. Thus, the near-identity of PA and absorption signals in the $28\,000$ to $33\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region of the $S_2 \leftarrow S_0$ excitation region indicates little or no effect of vibronic coupling on $S_2 \rightarrow S_1$ or $S_2 \rightarrow S_0$ degradative routes.

Quantum yields: An $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ fluorescence has been reported⁵ and an ir CH stretching luminescence following excitation in $S_1 \leftarrow S_0$ has been observed¹⁴. Regardless of the verity of either report, it is a fact that the total emission quantum yield after $S_1 \leftarrow S_0$ excitation is essentially zero. Given that such is true, it should be possible to estimate the $S_2 \rightarrow S_0$ quantum yield of fluorescence.

The fluorescence conversion efficiency may be expressed either in term of a fluorescence energy yield

$$\eta_R = \frac{\iint N_e \bar{\nu}_e d\bar{\nu}_e dt}{\iint N_a \bar{\nu}_a d\bar{\nu}_a dt}$$

or a fluorescence quantum yield

$$\phi_F = \frac{\int N_e dt}{\int N_a dt}$$

where, N is the number of photons, $\bar{\nu}$ is an energy unit, and the subscripts a and e indicate absorption and emission, respectively. For a narrow band excitation, the fluorescence quantum yield can be expressed as

$$\phi_F = \eta_R \bar{\nu}_a / \bar{\nu}_e$$

where, $\bar{\nu}_a$ is the excitation frequency (cm^{-1}) and $\bar{\nu}_e$ is the barycenter frequency (cm^{-1}) of the fluorescence band. The photoacoustic signal, on the other hand, depends upon the heat conversion efficiency η_R which, in the absence of any photochemistry, is given by $\eta_R = 1 - \eta_{\text{PC}}$.

The estimation of $S_2 \rightarrow S_0$ fluorescence quantum yield is simplified by considering only single frequency excitation from S_0 to S_1 (and also S_2), time integrals being eliminated by considering total number of photons in the laser pulse. The null or nearly null quantum yield for $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ emissivity enables us to write the photoacoustic signal PA_1 for $S_1 \leftarrow S_0$ excitation as

$$PA_1 = k N_1 h \nu_1 (1 - 10^{-A_1})$$

where, k is a constant that relates deposited thermal energy to acoustic signal, N_1 is the number of incident photons of frequency ν_1 in the laser pulse, and A_1 is the absorbance of the sample at this same frequency. The normalised photoacoustic signal PA_1^* generated by the spectrometer is defined as

$$PA_1^* = \frac{k N_1 h \nu_1 (1 - 10^{-A_1})}{S_1 R_1 N_1 h \nu_1} \\ = \frac{k(1 - 10^{-A_1})}{S_1 R_1}$$

where, S_1 is the spectral responsivity of the photomultiplier tube at this wavelength, and R_1 is the polarisation dependent reflection coefficient of the beam splitter including, as needed, the additional attenuation required to reduce the reference beam intensity to measurable levels. Since the polarisation changes from horizontal to vertical when doubling crystals are used to generate the second harmonic for $S_2 \leftarrow S_0$ excitation, the value of R will also change by an amount which depends upon

angle and various other known characteristics of the beam splitter. All of these additional attenuation factors in R need not be known if the system remains undisturbed from measurement to measurement.

The photoacoustic signal PA_2 for $S_2 \leftarrow S_0$ excitation is

$$PA_2 = k(N_{a_2} h \nu_2 - N_{e_2} h \bar{\nu}_{e_2}) \\ = k N_{a_2} h \nu_2 \left(1 - \frac{\bar{\nu}_{e_2}}{\nu_2} \phi_{F_2}\right)$$

where, N_{a_2} is the number of photons of frequency ν_2 absorbed from the laser pulse, N_{e_2} is the number emitted at a mean frequency of $\bar{\nu}_{e_2}$, and ϕ_{F_2} is the quantum yield for $S_2 \rightarrow S_0$ fluorescence. The normalised photoacoustic signal PA_2^* is then given by

$$PA_2^* = \frac{k N_{a_2} h \nu_2}{S_2 R_2 N_2 h \nu_2} \left(1 - \frac{\bar{\nu}_{e_2}}{\nu_2} \phi_{F_2}\right)$$

Since $N_{a_2} = N_2 (1 - 10^{-A_2})$, where N_2 is the number of photons in the laser pulse at the $S_2 \leftarrow S_0$ excitation wavelength and the sample absorbance is A_2 , we may write

$$PA_2^* = \frac{k}{S_2 R_2} (1 - 10^{-A_2}) \left(1 - \frac{\bar{\nu}_{e_2}}{\nu_2} \phi_{F_2}\right)$$

The quantity k can be eliminated by combining the expressions for PA_1^* and PA_2^* , to yield

$$\phi_{F_2} = \left[1 - \frac{PA_2^* R_2 S_2 (1 - 10^{-A_1})}{PA_1^* R_1 S_1 (1 - 10^{-A_2})}\right] \frac{\nu_2}{\bar{\nu}_{e_2}}$$

Thus, the $S_2 \rightarrow S_0$ fluorescence quantum yield can be obtained if the sample absorbances for the $S_1 \leftarrow S_0$ and $S_2 \leftarrow S_0$ excitations are known at the wavelengths used to excite PA_1^* and PA_2^* , respectively. The absorption spectra for the $S_1 \leftarrow S_0$ and $S_2 \leftarrow S_0$ transitions in the origin band regions of azulene vapor at 50° were recorded on a Cary 217 using 10 cm absorption cells. The mean $S_2 \rightarrow S_0$ fluorescence ($\bar{\nu}_{e_2}$) was taken⁸ to be 26 300 cm^{-1} . Some prominent peaks in the $S_2 \leftarrow S_0$ and $S_1 \leftarrow S_0$ origin bands were used to calculate ϕ_{F_2} and its value was found to lie in the range 0 to 6%. The observed variation is largely attributable to spectral noise arising from the low value of A_1 . Our results for the fluorescence quantum yield from S_2 , while not very precise, agree with those obtained by more conventional means¹⁵, indicating the absence of any appreciable photochemistry, at least for low energy excitations into either S_1 or S_2 .

Photoacoustic spectroscopy has been used previously¹⁶ to estimate fluorescence quantum yields. Our method differs in that the non-emissivity of S_1 of azulene provides an internal standard for system calibration. Should the quantum yield of the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ emission happen not to be exactly zero, the value of ϕ_{F_2} , as obtained here, will constitute a minimum value. The analysis given here may be extended to the situation where both S_1 and S_2 are emissive and it can be shown that, in the absence of photochemistry and vibrational emissivity, a knowledge of the quantum yield of fluorescence from one state

can be used, *via* PA spectroscopy, to obtain that of the other. The method is particularly facile when one state is known not to emit because, in this instance, no photon yield measurements whatever are required. This latter appears to be the case for azulene.

In summary, the pulse-by-pulse signal normalisation technique described here is widely applicable. In addition, the extremely high sensitivity of the PA spectrometer permits the extraction of additional valuable information concerning azulene.

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